

Hypophysis: To be or not to be a neuroendocrine reservoir of canonical WNT signaling agonist lithium?

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Abstract

Hypophysis and WNT signaling play essential roles in development and homeostasis. Despite the hypophysis largely lacking or exhibiting low WNT activity after a critical developmental period, unlike the majority of other tissues, it can accumulate the WNT signaling agonist lithium. However, the precise role of this lithium uptake activity remains unclear. In this manuscript, I propose that the hypophysis may function as a lithium reservoir and releasing site in response to physiological demand. Whether lithium action occurs locally in the hypophysis or an endocrine manner needs further investigation.

Hypophysis is one of the evolutionarily conserved major endocrine interfaces. In addition to all its numerous endocrine functions, hypophysis is also one of the endocrine sites in which relatively higher levels of lithium have been reported. Studies in rats have shown that hypophysis and thyroid are enriched with Li^+ (2-3 times higher than plasma levels and 1.4 times higher than total brain levels) (Ebadi *et al.*, 1974; Levine *et al.*, 1993). Even though a majority of the studies have investigated the role of Li^+ in WNT signaling regulation, the physiological role of Li^+ is still under debate (Haimovich & Goldbourt, 2020). But then the question arises: why do neuroendocrine tissues such as the hypophysis accumulate Li^+ even though they lack or exhibit low WNT signaling activity after hypophyseal development? (Benz *et al.*, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2019) The other question is how are Li^+ sensed and stored in hypophyseal cells? Protein-based reservoirs and metallophores or chalkopores such as small-polypeptide-based small chelating molecules (methanobactin) have been reported in bacteria for other metal ions such as Copper (Kenney & Rosenzweig, 2012, 2018; Vita *et al.*, 2015). RNA-based riboceptors (riboswitch) for Li^+ with gene expression regulation functions have been demonstrated in bacteria (White *et al.*, 2022). But whether similar Li^+ sensing mechanisms exist in mammalian cells is unknown. Historically, neurohypophysis was thought to be the site of synthesis of neuropeptides oxytocin and vasopressin. However, we now understand that it primarily regulates and mediates neuropeptide release. My proposal suggesting that the hypophysis acts as a lithium reservoir aligns with the concept of tissues serving as putative metal reservoirs. An extreme example of this concept is illustrated by the 'lethal milk' mutation observed in mice (McCormick *et al.*, 2014). Studying such a hypothesis may help reveal the endocrine role of Li^+ , searching for Li^+ reservoirs (similar to zinc reservoirs such as metallothionein), and may aid in understanding the etiology of human diseases such as bipolar disorders.

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References

- Benz, F., Wichitnaowarat, V., Lehmann, M., Germano, R.F., Mihova, D., Macas, J., Adams, R.H., Taketo, M.M., Plate, K.-H., Guérit, S., Vanhollebeke, B., & Liebner, S. (2019) Low wnt/ β -catenin signaling determines leaky vessels in the subfornical organ and affects water homeostasis in mice. *Elife*, **8**, e43818.
- Ebadi, M.S., Simmons, V.J., Hendrickson, M.J., & Lacy, P.S. (1974) Pharmacokinetics of lithium and its regional distribution in rat brain. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, **27**, 324–329.
- Haimovich, A. & Goldbourn, A. (2020) How does the mood stabilizer lithium bind ATP, the energy currency of the cell: Insights from solid-state NMR. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects*, **1864**, 129456.
- Kenney, G.E. & Rosenzweig, A.C. (2012) Chemistry and biology of the copper chelator methanobactin. *ACS Chem Biol*, **7**, 260–268.
- Kenney, G.E. & Rosenzweig, A.C. (2018) Chalkophores. *Annu Rev Biochem*, **87**, 645–676.
- Levine, S., Saltzman, A., Katof, B., Meister, A., & Cooper, T.B. (1993) Lithium accumulation in the neurointermediate lobe of rat pituitary exceeds that in other endocrine glands. *Neuro endocrinol. lett*, **15**, 357–362.
- McCormick, N.H., Hennigar, S.R., Kiselyov, K., & Kelleher, S.L. (2014) The biology of zinc transport in mammary epithelial cells: implications for mammary gland development, lactation, and involution. *J Mammary Gland Biol Neoplasia*, **19**, 59–71.
- Vita, N., Platsaki, S., Baslé, A., Allen, S.J., Paterson, N.G., Crombie, A.T., Murrell, J.C., Waldron, K.J., & Dennison, C. (2015) A four-helix bundle stores copper for methane oxidation. *Nature*, **525**, 140–143.
- Wang, Y., Sabbagh, M.F., Gu, X., Rattner, A., Williams, J., & Nathans, J. (2019) Beta-catenin signaling regulates barrier-specific gene expression in circumventricular organ and ocular vasculatures. *Elife*, **8**, e43257.
- White, N., Sadeeshkumar, H., Sun, A., Sudarsan, N., & Breaker, R.R. (2022) Lithium-sensing riboswitch classes regulate expression of bacterial cation transporter genes. *Sci Rep*, **12**, 19145.